

HUQUQNI TARTIBGA SOLISHDA “HUQUQNI QO’LLASH” MASALASI

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Annotasiya: Maqolada huquqni tartibga solishning turlari va ular orasida huquqni qo'llash tushunchasi nima ekanligi haqida so'z boradi. Bundan tashqari huquqni qo'llash masalasining normativlari ham tushuntiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Huquq, tartib, mexanizm, subekt, yuridik.

Аннотация: В статье говорится о видах правового регулирования и понятии правоприменения среди них. Кроме того, разъясняются и нормы правоприменения.

Ключевые слова: Право, порядок, механизм, субъект, правопорядок.

Abstract: The article discusses the types of legal regulation and what the concept of law enforcement is among them. \In addition, the norms of law enforcement are also explained.

Keywords: Law, procedure, mechanism, subject, legal.

Huquqni tartibga solish mexanizmida harakatda bo'lgan turlicha yuridik choralarga bo'lgan talab, subyekt manfaatlarining ma'lum maqsadga erishishdaga har xil harakatlari bilan yoki yo'lda turgan (to'siq bo'layotgan) qarama-qarshiliklarning mavjudligi bilan aniklanadi. Huquqni tartibga solish mexanizmi huquq normativining (normativnosti prava) ijtimoiy munosabatlarini tartibga solishdagi o'tish jarayonining funksional tomonini ifoda etadi. Bu jarayon - uzoq davom etadigan bo'lib, u bir necha bosqichlarga (stadiya) bo'linadi, va natijada bu bosqichning har biriga bir qancha alohida yuridik choralar qo'llanilib, hammasi

birgalikda huquqni tartibga solish mexanizmini tashkil etadi. Huquqni tartibga solish o'z ichiga quyidagi bosqich (stadiya) larni qamrab oladi:

1) huquq normasini ipshab chiqish va umumiy ta'sirining belgilanishi (ijtimoiy munosabatlarni reglamentlash);

2) subyektiv huquq va subyektiv yuridik majburiyatlarni paydo bo'lishi;

3) subyektiv huquq va subyektiv yuridik majburiyatlarni tadbiq etish, ya'ni ularni ijtimoiy munosabatlar ishtirokchilarining hulqiga konkret va faktik singdirish jihatdan;

4) huquqni qo'llash.

Sosial-ijtimoiy normalarning obyektiv xarakteri quyidagi holatlar bilan aniqlanadi: a) ijtimoiy (sosial) normalar sosial tizimning o'z-o'zini tartibga solishdagi obyektiv talablardan kelib chiqadi (barqarorlik va tartibni ko'lab-kuvvatlash uchun);

b) ijtimoiy normalar ipshab chiqarishning subyektiv shartli ko'rinishi kishilarning faoliyati jarayonida vujudga keladi;

v) normalar, xarakteri ishlab chiqarish usuli va taqsimlash bilan aniqlanadigan munosabatlar almashuvidan ajralmagan holda bo'ladi.

Amalda bo'lishi va ta'minlanishiga qarab, sosial normalar quyidagicha tasniflanadi:

- hukuq normalari;
- axloq normalari;
- odatlar;
- korporativ (jamoat tashkilotlari normalari) normalar.

Tartibga solinadigan ijtimoiy munosabatlarning mazmuniy doirasiga qarab sosial normalarni quyidagicha tasniflanadi:

- siyosiy;
- tashkiliy;

- etik;
- estetik normalar.

Jumladan, sosial normalarning tasniflashning boshqa kriteriyalari ham bo'lib, ularga quyidagilar kiradi:

- tashkil topish usuliga qarab (ongli tartibda yoki o'z-o'zidan paydo bo'ladi (stixiyali);
- ifodalash yoki mustahkamlilik usuliga qarab (yozma, og'zaki, shakl).

Huquqni tartibga solishning yuqoridagi bosqichlariga tegishli holda, uning mexanizmini 4 ta asosiy elementi ajratiladi:

- 1) huquq normasi;
- 2) huquqiy munosabatlar;
- 3) huquq va majburiyatlarni tadbiq etish;
- 4) huquqni qo'llash aktlari.

Xuquq normasi - huquqni tartibga solishdagi boshlang'ich yuridik baza sifatida yuzaga chiqadi, chunki uning dispozitsiyasida shakllangan va zarur bo'lgan holning modeli o'z ifodasini topadi. Xuquqiy munosabatlar - huquq normalarini kim tomonidan qanday bajarilishini anikdashga yordam beruvchi bosh vosita bo'lib hisoblanadi. Xuquq va majburiyatlarni tadbiq etish - bu subyektlarning faktik holqi. Bu yerda huquqni tartibga solish: mexanizmi o'z harkatini tugatadi, sababi subyektlarning faktik va real holqi (povedenie) ta'minlanadi, sababi qonun chiqaruvchining amri nimaga qaratilgan bo'lsa, u o'z natijasiga erishadi.

Huquqni tartibga solish mexanizmining qaysi elementlari oldin yoki keyin qo'llanilishi to'g'risida aytiladigan bo'lsa, uning quyidagi ikki xili to'g'risida to'xtaladi:

- a) oddiy tartibga solish - shunday jarayonki, bunda davlatning bitta hokimiyatlik akti, ayni normativ akti qo'llanib, akt karatilgan hukuk, va majburiyatlarning individualligini subyektlarning o'zlari ta'minlaydilar;

b) murakkab tartibga solish - shunday jarayonki, davlat hokimiyatlilik xarakteriga ega bo'lgan ikkita akt qo'llanib ulardan bittasi normativ akt, ikkinchisi esa huquq normalarini qo'llash akti bo'ladi. Huquqiy ta'sir qilish mexanizmi yoki huquqiy tartibga solish mexnizmida yuridik normalar bosh rolni o'ynaydi, chunki huquqiy normalar huquqiy tartibga solishning asosini shakllantiradi (tashkil etadi). Savol tug'iladi, qaysi vaqtdan boshlab huquqii tartibga solish yoki huquqni tartibga solish mexanizmining harakatga kelish sababi nimada? degan. Bu to'g'rida har xil fikr (javob)lar bo'lib, jumladan, P.Ye.Nedbaylo hisoblaydiki, yuridik normaning tartibga solish roli uning harakatga kelish (kirish) vaqtdan boshlanadi, desa; V.SHeyndlin aytishicha, bu holat yuridik normaning bosilib chiqishi (izdanie) dan boshlanadi. Aniqroq qilib aytganda, xukuqni tartibga solish yuridik normaning bosilib chiqish yoki kuchga kirish paytidan boshlanmasdan, balkim huquqiy normalarida belgalangan tartibda yuridik faktlarning paydo bo'lishi vaqtdan boshlanadi. Huquqni tartibga solish mexanizmida dinamika nuqtai nazaridan, asosiy og'irlik (nagruzka) ni konkret huquqiy munosabatlar o'z bo'ynga oladi.

Bu yerda huquqiy munosabatlar deganda, yuridik huquq va majburiyatlarning mavjudligi bilan xarakterlanadigan, davlatning majburlov (yoki kafolatlovchi) kuchlari bilan qo'llab-quvvatlanadigan, huquq normalariga asosan vujudga keladigan, shaxslar o'rtasidagi individuallashgan ijtimoiy aloqalar tushuniladi.

Huquqni tartibga solish mexanizmi huquqiy munosabatlar orqali xarakatga keladi, va uning vositaligida huquq normalarini tadbiq etish ro'y beradi. SHaxslar o'rtasidaga (huquqiy munosabat ishtirokchilari) aloqalar ma'lum individuallashgan xarakterga zga bo'lib, u yoki bu subyektlar huquqiy munosabati ishtiroxchilari bo'lgan zahotiyuq, ularning davlat bilan aloqasi huquq va majburiyatlar orqali konkretlashadi.

Taraflar (ishtirokchilar) ning yuridik holati (ahvoli) yoki o'zaro aloqalari (oddiy aloqa bo'lib qolmaydi, sababi birg tarafga hukuq yuklatilsa, ikkinchi tomonga har xil majburiyat yuklatiladi) huquq munosabatlarida har xil (turlicha) aniqlanadi.

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